

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF DEEP EXCAVATION IN SOFT SOILS WITH SOLDIER PILES PROTECTION CONSIDERING THE STRAIN LEVEL FOR STIFFNESS OF THE SOILS

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ABSTRACT: Excavation is one of the most common work found in a project, especially in a high-rise building project. Present day, excavation goes deeper and sometimes it is constructed on soft soils. Therefore, an appropriate analysis must be conducted in order to assure a safe excavation.

A case study takes place in an apartment project in Central Jakarta, Indonesia. The excavation is about 12 m depth, with free-standing soldier piles protection. Soil stratification of the project consists of four layers, with 6 m of soft clay at the top layer. At the same time, the neighborhood of the project is also crowded by residential buildings.

There are some soil models that commonly used in deep excavation analysis. Two of them are hyperbolic model and Mohr-Coulomb model. This paper discusses the use of hyperbolic soil model in excavation analysis using finite element method, considering the strain level. Strain level checking conducted at near of soldier piles in order to predict appropriate value of soil modulus. The use of Mohr-Coulomb model is also conducted for soldier piles deformation comparison. The soldier piles deformation profile from hyperbolic model and Mohr-Coulomb model then compared to inclinometer reading. The results show that hyperbolic soil model gives similar deformation profile, both shape and value of deformation, compared to inclinometer reading. Hyperbolic soil model is quite capable and accurate to model deep excavation problem.

Keywords: Deep excavation, soft soils, finite element analysis, hyperbolic soil model, strain level

INTRODUCTION

Excavation is one of the major challenges for practical engineers. The deeper the excavation, the more complex the analysis. Tools today such as finite element method, may become the best tool for the analysis. However, in geotechnical engineering, there are some soil models that commonly used to simulate soil behavior such as hyperbolic model, elastoplastic model, and Cam-clay model. The three models have their own characteristics to simulate stress-strain behavior of the soil.

Deep excavation in soft clay generally causes large wall deflection, which can endanger workers and adjacent buildings. Therefore, this problem should be the one of main concern and must be understood properly. Appropriate selection of soil model must be done in order to simulate the actual soil behavior, so the deflection of the retaining wall can be predicted accurately. This paper presents two

soil model for modeling deep excavation namely Elastoplastic Model (Mohr-Coulomb Model) and Hyperbolic Model. Excavation model was taken from apartment project (Ciputra World II) at Central Jakarta, Indonesia. It is a free-standing soldier piles used to protect the average 12.5 m excavation. Figure 1 shows the general view of the excavation.

Figure 1. Soldier piles used for protection of basement excavation

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SOIL STRATIFICATION AND SITE CONDITION

Soil investigation at Ciputra World II project consisted of 9 boreholes, and 7 CPTs, as shown in Figure 2. Due to large excavation areas, it is decided to analyze particular section. This paper will only focus on section 5 (4-point star mark), which is the location of analysis. Borehole (BH-6) was chosen for determining soil stratification because it is the nearest

borehole from the location of analysis. Soil underneath consisted of 4 layers, with 11 m thick of silty clay at the surface layer. This surface silty clay layer was founded almost at all areas of the site with different thickness. The consistency of the silty clay is soft, with average value of N_{SPT} equals to 4. However, soil layers underneath the surface layer are relatively good soils, as can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Location of soil investigation

As shown in Figure 1, the neighborhood of site is crowded with buildings, so the boring machine cannot reach the boring location near the adjacent buildings. Therefore, in section 5, there are two types of bored piles installed to protect 19.0 m excavation, as shown in Figure 3. The length of bored pile type 1 and type 2 are 20.5 m and 28 m, respectively.

Figure 3. Soil stratification and retaining wall design

Excavation Monitoring by Inclinometer

Deformation of bored piles can be measured using inclinometer embedded into the piles during installation. Basically, it is assumed that the deformation of piles represented by the deviation of inclinometer. The measurement of deformation using inclinometer can be done from time to time during construction period.

In this project, there are 7 inclinometers installed both in bored piles type 1 and bored piles type 2. Depth of the inclinometers varied from 20.5 m to 24 m. Figure 4 shows the inclinometer reading. Figure 5 shows the general view of the excavation.

Figure 4. Inclinometer installed within bored piles

Figure 5. Two types of bored piles used to protect excavation

ANALYSIS METHOD

Analyses were conducted by using finite element-based program PLAXIS 2D. The behavior of soil modeled in two model namely MC Model and Hyperbolic Model (HS Model in PLAXIS 2D). The analyses only focus on the performance of retaining walls such as deformation and forces acting on the piles. Ground settlement and heaving are excluded from this study.

Constitutive Model

Selecting appropriate soil model in analyzing deep excavation is very important thing to do in order to get an accurate analyses results. Constitutive model explains about how the model simulate the stress-strain behavior of the soil. The explanation of the model used in this study is presented as follows.

Mohr-Coulomb Model (MC Model)

MC model is the simplest soil model amongst other models. The stress-strain relationship of the soil is modeled by bilinear line, namely linear elastic line and linear plastic line. Figure 6 shows the stress-strain curve of MC Model.

Figure 6. Stress-strain relationship of Mohr-Coulomb Model (Ou, 2006)

In MC Model, the soil stiffness is taken as E_{50} , which is constant throughout elastic zone until the

stress reach failure zone. In fact, soil never behaves linearly, which means the soil stiffness is never constant. The soil stiffness changes with the stress level within the soil mass (Gouw, 2014).

Another substantial that should be noted by engineer in using MC model: it is assumed that the soil unloading-reloading modulus, E_{ur} , is equal to E_{50} as can be seen in Figure Y. In reality, based on laboratory tests, under unloading-reloading condition, soils generally have much stiffer modulus compared to under loading condition. This means that in excavation problems, MC model can over-predict the analysis result.

Hyperbolic Model (HS Model)

Basically, hyperbolic model is used the soil stress-strain curve using hyperbolic function, by observing the characteristics of the soil stress-strain curve, such as the slope, degree of bending, and the ultimate strength. Duncan and Chang (1970), based on Konder's, study (1963) proposed that the soil stress-strain behaviors be expressed in hyperbolic curves, as shown in Figure 7. The hyperbolic curves can be expressed by the following equation (Ou, 2006).

$$\sigma_1 - \sigma_3 = \frac{\varepsilon}{\frac{1}{E_i} + \frac{\varepsilon}{(\sigma_1 - \sigma_3)_{ult}}} \quad (1)$$

Figure 7. Stress-strain behavior of Hyperbolic Model (Duncan & Chang, 1970)

In PLAXIS 2D, the hyperbolic model is known Hardening Soil Model (HS Model). One of the major differences between MC model and Hyperbolic Model is it used three types soil modulus to simulate stress-strain behavior namely the initial modulus, E_i , Oedometer modulus, E_{oed} , and unloading-reloading modulus, E_{ur} .

Geometry and Material Parameters

In this study, the deep excavation analysis is modeled by using plane strain model with 15-nodes element. The soil is modeled with Mohr-Coulomb and Hyperbolic Model. The soil layers are divided into four layer as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Deep excavation model

The soil stratification is determined from interpretation of soil tests (N_{SPT} and UDS samples). The uppermost layer is 11 m thick of silty clay with soft consistency (average $N_{SPT} = 4$). The second layer is 6 m thick of sandy silt with medium to stiff consistency (average $N_{SPT} = 30$). The third layer is 19 m thick of dense sand (average $N_{SPT} = 50$). The soldier piles is predicted to be embedded into this sand layer. And the fourth layer is 6 m thick of silty clay with stiff to hard consistency (average $N_{SPT} = 36$).

Engineering properties of the soil are derived from laboratory tests (TX-CU) and correlation graph. For excavation problems, it should be noted that the strain level near the retaining wall will produce small shear strains. The smaller shear strain, the higher soil modulus.

In this study, it is first assumed that shear strains produced near the bored piles will be 0.2% (for layer 2, 3, and 4). Therefore, the value of soil modulus was determined by using E vs ϵ graph (Yong, 2015),

which gave a correlation $E_u = 5 N_{SPT}$ (MPa). This correlation was applied to determine the soil modulus of layer 2, layer 3 and layer 4. The soil modulus of layer 1 was determined from TX-CU test.

For structural elements, it is assumed that the element behaves as elastic element. Therefore, the strength parameters of the structural element are the flexural stiffness (EI), and axial stiffness (EA).

Table 1 shows the input of structural parameters. Table 2 shows soil parameters for both MC and Hyperbolic Model are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Bored piles parameters

No	Name (dia)-spc	Type	EA (kN/m)	EI (kNm ² /m)	w (kN/m/m)	v
Type 1						
1	(□600)-800	Elastic	8.84×10^6	1.99×10^5	2.66	0.15
Type 2						
2	(□1000)-1200	Elastic	1.64×10^7	1.02×10^6	4.92	0.15

Table 2. Soil parameters for MC Model (a) and Hyperbolic Model (b)

No Layer	Name	γ_{unsat} (kPa)	γ_{sat} (kPa)	$k_x = k_y$ m/day	R_{inter}	v	$E^{ref} = E_{50}$ (kPa)	$c^{ref} = c_u$ (kPa)	ϕ °	ψ °
1	Silty Clay	15.5	16.5	8.60E-04	0.8	0.35	5702	37	0	0
2	Sandy Silt	15	16.5	8.60E-04	0.8	0.3	150000	100	0	0
3	Dense Sand	17	18	8.60E-03	0.9	0.3	250000	1	0	0
4	Silty Clay	16.5	17.5	8.60E-04	0.8	0.3	190000	270	0	0

(a)

No Layer	Name	γ_{unsat} (kPa)	γ_{sat} (kPa)	$k_x = k_y$ m/day	R_{inter}	m	$E^{ref} = E_i$ (kPa)	E_{oed} (kPa)	E_{ur} (kPa)	$c^{ref} = c'$ (kPa)	\square °
1	Silty Clay	15.5	16.5	8.60E-04	0.8	1	11760	18866	58800	32	19
2	Sandy Silt	15	16.5	8.60E-04	0.8	1	272700	272700	818200	175	30
3	Dense Sand	17	18	8.60E-03	0.9	0.5	454500	454500	909100	1	45
4	Silty Clay	16.5	17.5	8.60E-04	0.8	1	345500	345500	1036000	222	35

(b)

ANALYSIS RESULTS COMPARED WITH INCLINOMETER READING

The deformation profile on bored piles type 1 is shown in Figure 9. As can be seen from the figure, the deformation profile on the head of bored piles type 1 tend to shape vertical line. This may be happens because of the soil modulus of layer 1 is too high. For evaluating the value of the modulus, it is decided to check the strain level near the bored piles type 1. Figure 10 shows the strain level check near the bored piles type 1.

At the uppermost layer, it is clear that the shear strain at the layer is high, with maximum value of shear strain 1.75%. This value then re-plotted on the graph (Figure 11) to get new value of soil modulus ($E = x N_{SPT}$). This procedure, called the iteration, is done until the value of shear strain converge.

The iteration process can be seen on Figure 11. Iteration started with using the maximum value of shear strain 1.75%. This value plotted into the E vs e (Yong, 2015), so the value of E can be determined. The calculation process then re-conducted. Number 1 to 4 in Figure 11 show the iteration. From the

iteration, the value of shear strain was converged on 2.6 %, which gave the correlation of $E = 1.1 N_{SPT}$ (MPa). The soil modulus of layer 1 then corrected with the correlation. The corrected values for both MC and hyperbolic model are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Corrected soil modulus (Layer 1)

Before Strain Check		After Strain Check	
$E^{ref} = E_i$	= 11760 kPa	→	7200 kPa
E_{oed}	= 18866 kPa	→	15200 kPa
E_{ur}	= 58800 kPa	→	36000 kPa
E_{50} (MC model)	= 5702 kPa	→	4400 kPa

It should be noted that the correlation $E = 1.1 N_{SPT}$ (MPa) was applied only for layer 1. As can be seen in Figure 10, shear strains near bored piles type 1 from -11.0 m to -44.00 depth is very small (almost 0%). Therefore, soil modulus for layer 2, 3, and 4 must be corrected with the same iteration procedure.

After correcting the value of soil modulus, the analysis results can be seen in Figure 12 and Figure 13. The results both from MC and hyperbolic model give similar deformation profile compared with inclinometer reading.

Figure 9. Deformation on bored piles type 1 (before strain level checking)

Figure 10. Strain level check near bored piles type 1 (cross section A-A*)

Figure 11. Iteration process for correcting the value of soil modulus

Figure 12. Deformation of bored piles type 1 and type 2

Figure 13. Forces acting on bored piles type 1

CONCLUSION

Deep excavation analysis using Mohr-Coulomb and Hyperbolic model have been done and compared. The deformation result from Hyperbolic Model gives more similar profile than the result from MC Model. However, both Mohr-Coulomb and Hyperbolic Model has deviation from inclinometer reading.

For deep excavation problems, modeling using MC Model will over-predict the deformation result.

This is because the MC model uses a constant soil modulus. In fact, the soil modulus is never constant.

Strain level checking is very useful for correcting the value of soil modulus, especially for correcting soft soil modulus. It can be done by simple iteration until the value of shear strain converge. Furthermore, strain level checking may provide appropriate soil modulus for predicting the deformation of retaining walls.

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